

EPIDEMIOLOGICAL INVESTIGATIONS OF A PESTE DES PETITS RUMINANTS (PPR) OUTBREAK IN SOMALI REGION, ETHIOPIA

Photo taken in Korahe/Gashamo Sep 2014

Photo taken in Moyale/Eley Sep 2014

Photo taken in Worder/Tulhan Sep 2014

A Study Conducted for VSF Suisse by PRE Consultancy

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Figure 1: Map of Somali Region locating PPR outbreaks occurred in 2013 and 2014

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Research Background and Overview

This draft report describes a disease mapping study conducted to classify the highest priority Peste des petits ruminants (PPR) surveillance and control intervention areas in Ethiopian Somali Regional State. This is typically a strategy for the progressive control of PPR in Ethiopia that follows geographic approaches toward control and ultimately eradication of the most devastating small ruminant disease. Under the strategy for progressive control of PPR in Ethiopia, the VSF Suisse Ethiopia Country Office commissioned the epidemiological investigation of PPR outbreaks conducted in Ethiopian Somali Region. The Participatory Research Evaluation (PRE) Consultancy conducted the PPR outbreak investigation in collaboration with VSF Suisse. This was an initiative aimed to develop a practical action plan and guide the implementation of PPR surveillance and control program so as to carefully experiment and draw useful lessons that would determine the implementation approach of the strategy for the progressive control of PPR, and define the scope.

Peste des Petits Ruminants (PPR) is a disease of major economic importance and poses serious threat to sheep and goat production. It is an acute, highly contagious and fatal disease of sheep and goats caused by PPR virus (PPRV) that affects the livelihoods of poor people depending on milk and income derived from small ruminant production especially in pastoral areas where the disease is endemic. On average, the goat and sheep population of the studied communities was estimated to around 58.5% of the total livestock population.

The purpose of the participatory PPR outbreak investigation work was to gather first hand pastoralist and animal health professionals' opinions on the epidemiology of PPR as it occurs in sample districts of each study zone. The study covered Shebelle, Dollo, Korahe, Jerer, Fafen, Sity, Liben and Afder zones of Somali region and investigated outbreaks that were occurred between 2008 and 2014. Regrettably, it was not possible to access the Nogob zone due to insecurity problem although the VSF Suisse had planned doing the assessment in Fiq and Hamero districts of the zone in both second and third assessment rounds, May 2014 and September 2014.

The field assessment was conducted in two rounds: June 2013 in Korahe zone and September 2014 in Shebelle, Dollo, Jerer, Fafen, Sity, Liben and Afder zones. A total of 21 districts selected in consultation with the region and zone veterinary services based on history of at least one PPR outbreak reported from the district between 2010 and 2014 to have focused on the most recent outbreaks were covered across the 9 zones of the region. Within each sample district, specific sites for the study were selected in consultation with district veterinary unit based on the geographic position and history of PPR outbreak with a focus on sites located close to Somalia and Kenya, as well as neighboring zones where PPR outbreak occurred since 2010 where applicable.

Information on PPR outbreaks and vaccine interventions were collected both from pastoralists and government employee animal health professionals assigned to study zones and districts through focus group discussion and key informant interview methods respectively. The focus group discussion participants were asked to identify and describe symptoms of major small ruminant diseases existing in their area. The identified diseases were then considered for proportional pilings. The subsequent steps focused on the labelling locally given to the PPR, such as disease occurrence patterns and impact, and history of vaccination programs. The last outbreak was then considered for proportional pilings to assess infection and mortality rates. The impact of the last PPR outbreak on survivor animals were identified as weight loss, reduced milk production and increased veterinary expenses, which were also considered for matrix scoring.

Additional participatory assessments were carried out with the government animal health professionals working in the study districts. Typically government animal health professionals were asked to describe vaccine interventions implemented in their zone and district during the recent outbreak or years. The government animal health professionals working with the district veterinary units also provided the study with written information on the timing and duration of recent vaccination events as well as the amount of vaccines utilized during each vaccination event.

The assessment documented a total of 45 PPR outbreaks affected a total of 20 districts identified under eight zones for the PPR outbreak assessment work prioritized to districts involved in outbreaks occurred between 2010 and 2014. During this period, a total of 64 vaccination campaigns were also conducted mostly following the outbreaks, with 2,866,000 doses of PPR vaccine. On average, the number of animals vaccinated per kebele per vaccination round was calculated at 5,580 doses. The impact of outbreak triggered vaccinations carried out with such small amount of vaccines is expected to be very low if not nil. On the one hand, the outbreak period calculated at around 4 months meant that cases to have occurred over more than a single incubation periods, suggesting that an effective emergency vaccination may have resulted in shorter duration of those outbreaks.

1.2 The Primary Purpose and Scope of the Study

The VSF Suisse aimed to identify the highest priority intervention areas of the Region and therefore launch the VSF Suisse, MOA and FAO partnership program. The primary purpose of the PPR outbreak investigation work is to assist the VSF Suisse, Ministry of Agriculture (MoA), FAO and LCNRDB of Somali Region better understand and therefore implement the strategy for the progressive control of PPR in Ethiopian Somali Region. Accordingly, the study was designed with a view to filling knowledge gaps including factors that can potentially lead-to outbreaks in relatively low risk areas and assess the existing capacities and constraints in detecting and containing outbreaks through appropriate measures.

This study represents a key step to set an informed PPR surveillance and control strategy development and priorities in the Region through a participatory process that involves all relevant strategy stakeholders. In doing so, the study process was meant to collect the

perceptions of different actors in the strategy for the progressive control of PPR in Ethiopian Somali Region and establish descriptions of the benefits of pastoralists and service providers from this strategy. The study analyzed key issues related to the current PPR outbreak control practice to make recommendations that can be taken forward by the MoA, FAO and other key stakeholders.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Study Design

The study had two components: analysis of records kept on vaccinations conducted following PPR outbreaks by district veterinary units and information collected from pastoralists through focus group discussion and key informant interview methods. The key informant interview component also involved CAHWs and local animal health professionals who also participated in the vaccination campaigns conducted in response to PPR outbreaks investigated. Emergency vaccination was one of the main factors considered for the patterns and economic impact of the investigated outbreaks. The field assessments were conducted in selected sites by five teams in September 2014.

2.2 Selection of Study Sites

Based on the insecurity constraint, it was agreed that the study should be limited to secure geographical areas of the strategy for progressive control of PPR in Ethiopia project intervention zones of Somali region to have exclude the Nogob zone. During the study design, the remaining 8 zones were organized into six clusters: Liben zone, Afdar zone, Sity and Fafen zones, Shebelle and Korahe zones, Dollo (X-Worder) zone and Jerer and Korahe zones. However, the plan was to visit the Korahe and Jerer zones covered by a similar study conducted in April and June 2013 only when the information from Shebelle and Dollo zones suggests cross transmission between zones. Accordingly, the tem deployed to Dollo zone visited the Gashamo district of Korahe zone where active case displayed on the cover page was encountered.

The selection of study district was largely based on a combination of two criteria; firstly, the perceived potential learning benefits for each study zone, and secondly the relative position of that district to the zone specifically risk of PPR being introduced from neighboring zone or country such as Kenya and Somalia. Although the field assessment was prioritized to districts where vaccination was conducted during the last years in response to PPR outbreak, the study also collected general information on all outbreaks occurred between 2008 and 2014.

2.3 Study Team Organization

Table 1 shows the size and composition of study teams. Five teams comprised of two persons each, veterinarian and animal health assistant, conducted field-level assessment

under close supervision of senior participatory research specialist with over 20 experience in participatory research methods. There was also a veterinarian assigned by LCRNDB to represent the region veterinary department in the outbreak investigation work.

Table 1: List of study teams

Team members	Zone	District
Dr. Adamu Girma, Dr. Abdulahi Abdi and Abdinur Ali	Shebelle	Adadle, Kelafo and Mustahil
Dr. Ali, Tatek G/Medhin and Mohamed Ahmed	Sity and Fafen	Harshin, Kebribeyah, Babile, Shinille and Erer
Dr. Abdo Shifa and Muktar Abdi	Afder zone	Hargelle, Chereti and Dollo Bay
Dr. Yasin and Yenalem Seyoum	Dollo and Korah	Woder, Galadid and Gashamo
Drs. Tefera Sime and Fisseha Abinet	Liben	Moyale, Hudet and Mubarek
Dr. Adamu Girma and Muktar Abdi	Liben	Dhekasuftu, Filtu and Dollo Ado

2.4 Data Collection

Both qualitative and quantitative research instruments were used, and were designed in consultation with VSF Suisse experts based in Addis Ababa and field areas. The field-level PPR outbreak investigation was conducted April 4 to 30, 2014. The study applied a standardized checklist with number of counters to be applied per variable and data sheet to generate uniform data across zones, districts and sites. Information was collected using participatory techniques and tools through focus group discussion and key informant interview methods as follows:

Informant groups – these informants provided quantitative and qualitative data used for characterizing PPR outbreaks occurred during the study period fixed as the period between 2008 and September 2014. Specifically, these informants identified and scored:

- Relative importance and seasonal prevalence of major goat and sheep diseases existing in their area.
- Start and ending time of PPR outbreaks witnessed during the study period, as year, season and month.
- Where applicable, start month of emergency vaccinations triggered by each of the identified outbreaks.
- Proportion developed symptom of PPR disease of the small ruminant population existed at onset of the last outbreak and proportion of cases ended fatal among animals born before and after the preceded PPR outbreak.
- Impact of PPR on production and reproductively performances of affected animals
- Sex composition of small ruminant populations.
- Map of outbreak spots and small ruminant markets.

Key informants – this refers to government animal health staff based in study districts, CAHWs questioned on issues related to the timeliness and coverage of outbreak driven vaccination and women pastoralists asked age at first mating of female goats and sheep, proportion aborting and normal births surviving to weaning age.

Finally, the data was summarized and converted into figures using Microsoft Office Excel 2007, and the outcomes are covered under four main sections.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Small Ruminant Production in Somali Region

3.1.1 Major purposes of goat and sheep production

The economic utility of goat and sheep among the studied communities includes its function as source of milk and meat food and cash money. Skin and hide used for different purposes and prestige were also provided due credit in all places. The comparative value of the major benefits obtained from goat and sheep production to study communities is presented in Table 2. On average, the number of objects directed to cash benefit is the largest in a single scoring in both goat and sheep, with milk and meat collected the second largest score respectively. Majority of the studied communities (16 out of 25) were not used to sheep milk stood last with around 10% average score.

Figure 2 shows the species mix of livestock population of the study area in 2010 and 2014. The mean score of the proportional pilings showed an around 5% increment resulted over five-year period for cattle while that of small ruminants and camels declined by around 3% and 2% proportionally. However, the percentage share of goats in the livestock population was the highest followed by that of sheep throughout, indicating the importance of these species to Somali pastoralists. Currently, goat and sheep account for around 55 per cent of the total livestock population of the area.

Table 2: Major purpose of goat and sheep production

Benefit	Relative importance of benefits, proportion (%)	
	Goat	Sheep
Milk food	31	9.9
Cash income	34	54
Meat food	30	22.9
Other (skin and prestige)	5.4	13.2

Figure 2: Proportion (%) livestock population mix in 2010 and 2014

3.1.2 Major small ruminant production constraints

The study identified major goat and sheep production constraints that were ranked through proportional piling method. Table 3 provides the list and relative importance of the identified production constraints. Disease ranked first with an average score of 50% of the overall constraints, as an all time problem. The same informants were also asked to identify and compare the relative importance of specific diseases considered during proportional piling exercise carried out for production constraints.

Figure 3 illustrates the relative importance of major diseases identified as CCPP, Pox, HS, PPR, Anthrax, Blackleg, NSD and Mange. The figure was based on proportional pilings conducted using 100 objects by participants in 25 focus group discussions. From the figure, the mean proportional piling scores were significantly lower for HS, Anthrax and Blackleg diseases that can be effectively treated with antibiotics and acaricides at reasonable cost relative to PPR, CCPP and Pox, with the largest number of objects directed to PPR in a single scoring.

Table 3: Relative importance of production constraints

Constraint	Relative importance, proportion (%)
Disease	50
Drought	37
Predator	11
Other/theft	2

Figure 3: Comparison of selected goat and sheep diseases for overall relative importance

3.1.3 Effect of PPR outbreak on small ruminant production

The impact assessment was designed to produce a qualitative and quantitative analysis of PPR disease with a focus on the PPR outbreak occurred last in each study. Increased mortality, reduced milk production, increased abortion and weight loss as proxy indicator for reduced cash derived from sale of livestock by owners were used as the main indicator of livelihoods impact. The design of the study took account of death and abortion caused by non-PPR diseases through assigning certain number of objects as nominal score. The scoring was done for each of the indicators identified by the community. These are mortality, milk production, body weight and expenditure on animal drugs.

Finally, the impact of the PPR disease in animals affected by the last outbreak on household economy in terms of indicators indicated above, as well as household treatment expense incurred from mass medication of affected animals was calculated using the number of objects removed or added to the number of objects assigned per indicator as a benchmark for production loss resulted in the absence of PPR outbreak. The result of proportional pilings showed that on average:

- Goat and sheep mortality and abortion increased from 10% at normal time to around 40% and 18% at times of PPR outbreak respectively.
- Milk production and body condition of goats and sheep affected by PPR disease decreased around 41% and 38% below the normal mil off-take and body condition respectively.

- Veterinary cost increased from 10% at normal time to around 46% specifically due to antibiotics applied by owners of PPR-affected animals, as curative treatment against secondary infection

Figure 4: Effect of PPR outbreak on small ruminant production and productivity

3.2 Prevalence and Distribution of PPR Outbreaks in Somali Region

3.2.1 Epidemiological observations

Information on year and start season/month and course of outbreak, source of infection, proportion infected of the total population existed during the last outbreak, proportion died and survived of the portion infected were recorded for each species. During the proportional piling, informants were asked to split the total population existed during the last outbreak as well as the proportion infected and died of the disease into two: proportion born before and after the immediately preceded outbreak. The proportional piling results and information on the course of the disease sourced from same informant groups were used to assess the impact of the disease against time interval between consecutive outbreaks, and also, to draw epidemiological curve to see the magnitude and succession of the outbreaks.

The normal sex ratio of the goat and sheep populations was also assessed through proportional piling method. On average, females accounted for around 66.6 % and 67.9 % of the total goat and sheep populations in the studied areas respectively. Average age at first mating of female goats and sheep, lactation length, and time interval between consecutive birth events, abortion and births surviving to weaning age were also collected through focus group discussions with men and women, and key informant interviews

mostly with women (Table 4). These data were used to estimate likely susceptible population that worth considering for vaccination during different vaccination rounds of the two-year vaccine intervention period suggested under the strategy for the progressive control of PPR in each target location.

Table 4: Age and sex composition of goat and sheep populations

Age and sex composition of goat and sheep flocks, proportion (%)					
Age group	Goat		Sheep		Remark
	Female	Male	Female	Male	
All age groups	66.6	33.4	67.9	32.1	The sex and age mix is always stable due to different off-take reasons such as culling.
≥6 month old	60.8	31.7	60.4	30.4	
Age at 1 st mating, month	18		12		
Birth interval, month	8.44		8.37		
Abortion (%)	10.5		5.6		
Births surviving (%)	78.33		84.68		
Annual entry from birth	39.39		46.40		

3.2.2 Disease diagnosis skill of pastoralists

The clinical diagnostic skills of pastoralists have been checked by veterinarians against the typical symptoms of PPR disease incorporated into the assessment checklist, and this can be seen in Table 5. A further means of cross-checking was a comparison of the infection rates and CFRs reported by pastoralists, with the literature on PPR outbreaks in pastoral areas. Ideally, the proportional piling results from pastoralists would have been cross-checked against records kept by local veterinary units for those outbreaks. This level of detailed information was not available with district and region veterinary units.

Table 6 provides local names of PPR by location. All names relate to symptoms mainly diarrhoea and respiratory problem with diarrhoea, except *Amberur* a popular Somali name of Orf that refers to mouth lesion. Diarrhoea and discharges are the most frequently noted signs after which the disease was named, example *sombeb-har* and *dif-har*. While *Sombeb* means 'lung' is a name given both to CCPP and CBPP by Somali pastoralists, *har* means diarrhoea was added to describe PPR. However, massive mortality and comparatively longer intervals between consecutive outbreaks was the main criteria applied by pastoralists to differentiate between PPR and CCPP outbreaks. Figure 4 provides photos of cases called *Susun*, *Hulumbe*, *Cholera* and *sombeb-har* by Somali pastoralists.

Table 5: Checklist for pastoralists' descriptions of PPR and simulating diseases

Disease	Local name	Meaning of name	Typical symptoms
CCPP			Fever, coughing, nasal discharge, grunting, walks with difficulty, contagious, high mortality in untreated cases. Informants must <i>mention that the disease did not affect sheep</i> '
PPR like disease			High fever, depression, anorexia, pneumonia, tearing, oral and nasal discharge, oral erosion, diarrhea, emaciation and massive mortality. Informants must <i>mention that the disease</i>

<i>affected both goats and sheep</i>	
Nairobi Sheep Disease	Diarrhea mixed with mucus and blood, transmits between animals, sheep die more than goat, tick borne. Informants must <i>mention that the disease killed more sheep than goats and/or the disease transmitted by tick</i>

Table 6: Local names of PPR disease

Location	Name	Remark
Warder, Galadid and Gashamo	Sombeb-har	It means Lung disease with diarrhea
Dollo bay	Debekerub	Debekerub was a Somali name of RP disease means diarrhoea
Hargelle and Chereti	Cholera and Hulumbe	Cholera refers to diarrhoea
Harshin	Susun, Sombeb-har	Susun means horrible appearance
Shinille	Hulumbe, Chlera, Susun, Debekerub	All names refer to diarrhoea
Erer	Hulumbe, Cholera, Susun and Sombeb-har	
Babile	Cholera and Hulumbe	Diarrhoea
Kebribeyah	Har, Hulumbe and Cholera	Har means diarrhoea
Adadle, mustahil and Kelafo	Hulumbe	
Moyale and Hudet	Cholera and Amberur	Amberur is a popular name of orf that refers to mouth lesions
Mubarek	Cholera, Amberur and Albati	Albati is diarrhoea in Oromo language
Dhekasuftu, Filtu and Dollo	Dif-har	Nasal discharge and diarrhoea

Figure 4: Photos of cases displayed to experts as PPR by Somali pastoralists

3.2.3 Estimating Infection and Case Fatality Rates in the Last PPR Outbreak

Data used for measuring infection rate and case fatality rate (CFR) was derived through proportional piling exercises facilitated with focus group discussion participants. The proportional piling method for estimation of infection and CFR partly depends on the ability of informants to diagnose the PPR disease with reasonable accuracy. Such diagnosis uses their clinical observations and recognition of epidemiological factors such as the occurrence patterns of disease, contact between flocks, exposure to infectious cases and other factors.

In this study, data from some of the proportional pilings conducted on outbreaks said to have affected the study area from July or August through to the time of this assessment in September 2014 were discarded due to two reasons. Firstly, it is essential that the pastoralists display active cases to epidemiologists facilitated the discussions that could have produced photos of cases as physical evidence. Secondly, the local veterinary services were supposed to respond first in reporting rumors to concerned bodies. Given the especial importance of PPR led-to the strategy for progressive control of PPR in Ethiopia, it is essential that any ongoing PPR outbreak including rumors are verified and confirmed through laboratory methods by region and Federal veterinary services.

A retrospective assessment can also be constrained by recall bias. Table 7 shows the start time of the outbreaks assessed for infection and case fatality rates. The time of the last outbreak varied from place to place, with 13, 7, 3, 1 and 3 of the 27 total study sites affected last in 2014, 2013, 2012, 2011 and 2010 respectively. However, the infection rate and CFR presented in this report was limited to outbreaks occurred between 2012 and 2014.

The selection of outbreaks for measuring infection and case fatality rates was largely based on history emergency vaccination being conducted following those outbreaks by district government veterinary units with the support NGOs operating in their area such as HCS and Save the Children in Shinille and Adadle study districts respectively. FAO also funded vaccinations conducted in response to outbreaks such as in Hargelle and Chereti area in 2013 through the region LCNRDB.

It should be noted a copy of written feedback provided to the Dhekasuft district veterinary unit by the National Animal Health Diagnostic and Investigation Center (NAHDIC) on samples collected for the purpose of detecting antigen in November 2013 following outbreak tentatively diagnosed as PPR that also drove emergency vaccination showed the test result to be negative for PPR, but positive for antibodies perhaps due to the timing of the sampling event. However, the laboratory experts considered botulism as one of the likely causes of the outbreak investigated.

Table 8 illustrates the result of proportional pilings on infection and case fatality rates. As is expected to be, the average scores assigned to the proportion of animals developed symptoms of the PPR disease and cases ended fatal both are lower for the group existed during the preceded outbreak compared with the group born after. On average, the proportion existed during the preceded outbreak of the population affected by the last

outbreak was calculated at 71.5% and 28.5% respectively. The proportion infected of total population of the groups born before and after the previous outbreak respectively was estimated to 46 per cent and 62.5 per cent, with around 52 per cent and 65 per cent of the cases ended fatal on average. Proportionally, the group born after the previous outbreak were subjected to infection and death approximately 1.4 times and 1.2 times more than the ones existed during the previous outbreak, and the interval between the onsets of the last two outbreaks selected for infection and case fatality rates assessment was around 26 months on average.

Table 7: Start time of outbreaks used for infection and case fatality rates measurement

District/Site	Last outbreak		Previous outbreak	
	Month	Year	Month	Year
Shinile/Dhegahjebis	June	2014	April	2013
Kebribeyah/Dibile	June	2014	November	2012
Erer/Hurso	April	2014	April	2012
Harshin/Bel-asie	July	2014	March	2012
Wardher/Tulhan	June	2014	June	2009
Galadin/Qoloan	February	2014	March	2013
Babile/Dhereto	June	2014	February	2012
Mustahil/Danyere	January	2013	April	2010
Adadle/Urgugora	March	2012	April	2010
Dollo/Dhaytulu	February	2014	November	2011
Filtu/Ayile	November	2013	April	2010
Dekasuftu/Deka	November	2013	December	2010
Moyale/Fayo	July	2013	September	2012

Table 8: Comparison of infection and case fatality rates for the last outbreak in population born before and after previous PPR outbreak

Proportion infected of the total population and died of the proportion developed symptoms of PPR during the last outbreak		
Proportion	Born before previous outbreak (%)	Born after previous outbreak (%)
Total population existed during last outbreak	71.5	28.5
Infected during last outbreak	32.9	17.8
Died of the last outbreak	17.2	11.6
Infection Rate	46.0	62.5
Case Fatality Rate	52.3	65.2

3.2.4 Outbreak reporting and response systems

The study also aimed to identify and briefly evaluate the existing animal disease outbreak reporting and response mechanisms. In the analysis of the disease outbreak reporting and response systems, the framework combined 4 sets of indicators: timely, reliable, critical and necessary to evaluate the past practices. The next step was to see how necessary each

response, i.e. whether it is the most economical way of controlling the disease. Timely + Reliable + Critical + Necessary = Essential.

The vaccination-based outbreak control system was evaluated based on timing and coverage of vaccinations conducted in response to PPR outbreaks investigated. Particular attention was given to intervals between onset of outbreak and vaccination events. The observed disease outbreak reporting and response mechanisms are as next.

- Kebele chairmen who often report to district administration offices are primary source of information on new outbreaks to the district veterinary units as well as the region LCNRDB mainly through phone calls.
- In majority of the cases especially in outbreaks occurred in districts covered by NGOs, the district administration offices mobilized resources available both with the district veterinary units mainly staff and veterinary drugs and vehicle and per-diem used for emergency vaccinations conducted following outbreaks.
- FAO and the LCNRDB were the most frequently mentioned source of vaccines and funding used for PPR vaccination conducted during the study period.
- The LCNRDB also mobilized veterinarians working with region veterinary department and the Regional Veterinary Diagnostic and Research Laboratory (RVDRL) based in Jigjiga town along with diagnostic kits and veterinary drugs to make tentative diagnosis and/or take samples coordinate emergency vaccination programs.
- In few outbreaks that involved laboratory investigation work, the RVDRL was responsible for collecting and submitting serum samples to the National Animal Health, Diagnostic and Investigation Center (NAHDIC) based in Sebeta.
- In November 2013, the NAHDIC also collected samples tested both for PPR antigen and antibodies from Liben zone specifically Dhekasuft following outbreak.
- The responses of all region level key stakeholders including FAO and NGOs operating in areas where PPR outbreaks occurred is highly appreciated, and this directly relates to efficiency of the response system. The LCNRDB's responses to outbreaks reported by kebele chair persons through district administration offices or district veterinary units also recognizes that herders' participation is critical determinant of success in any crucial role in disease control programs.

Given the remoteness of the outbreak-affected areas and the critical resource constraints existing at all levels, efforts made to contain outbreaks investigated were highly recognized despite the onset of outbreak and vaccination events happened at around two and half months interval on average. A number of uninvestigated rumors of PPR outbreaks encountered during this assessment in September 2014 are another issue of critical concern.

4. DISEASE TRANSMISSION MODELING

4.1 Understanding Disease Transmission Mechanisms

To prioritize zones and districts with the strategy for progressive control of PPR in Somali region, we must fully understand the effect of vaccination on between-zone/district transmission. It is therefore important to extrapolate small-scale kebele level vaccinations that test the effectiveness of a vaccine to a bigger (i.e. district and zone) population. For this purpose, the outbreak triggered vaccinations carried out during the last three years is thought most appropriate.

As a consequence, this PPR outbreak mapping was required to better understand the transmission risks between different zones and districts of the Somali region to decide whether to class them as endemic and disease-free areas. Apart from the seasonal and drought-induced movement associated transmission risk, further risk analysis was conducted using markets and trade routes.

Interestingly, the magnitude and course of the assessed outbreaks shows that neither local livestock markets nor geographic proximity had played roles in the disease transmission process, as the disease failed to transmit between populations depended on same markets being tended in adjacent kebeles. When selecting vaccine intervention sites for strategy for progressive control of PPR in Somali region and may be in all pastoral areas, there is a need to assume that the past outbreaks were more due to susceptible population built over time than disease transmission between populations given the limited evidence produced so far. This is to mean that the implementing agencies need to have a sound contingency plan to deal with outbreaks if the disease occurs outside the present vaccine intervention areas.

4.2 Predicting cross boarder PPR transmission risks and mechanisms

Both drought-driven cross border migration and the small ruminants marketing across the border with Somalia and Kenya route of between-country PPR transmission have been given due attention in this study. This was because the cause of outbreaks occurred in boarder districts like Moyale often following post-drought rains was thought to be cross boarder transmission. This thought was considered with the aim of predicting PPR transmission between countries, regions, zones and districts.

Accordingly, the drought-driven cross boarder livestock migration was found to be important between countries and region transmission mechanism. Potentially, the small ruminants marketing across the border with Somalia appeared to be more important in Worder and Galadin districts, Dollo/Worder zone in this study. Livestock marketing, mainly across the border with Somaliland and into the Gulf states, generates enormous revenues for livestock owners, traders and marketing agents in this area. The informal marketing system is sophisticated, but the federal government has been working hard to stop this unregulated market channel. This export route is always subject to unpredictable

but devastating disruption, and the risk of trade animals being confiscated by Ethiopian defense force is on increasing.

As a consequence, the Somaliland small ruminant exporters and their partners strongly linked to Somali pastoralists in Ethiopia have always been trucking trade animals especially small ruminants from ports to potential pasture fields located in the Worder study district at times of export market supply disruption. The traders' practice of trucking trade animals from port to potential pasture fields has also been adopted by Ethiopian Somali pastoralists. In this area, pastoralists have now replaced the traditional practice of undertaking long journey to distant located better potential pasture and water resources with trucking said to have helped reducing stress used to be caused to the drought-affected animals from long journey.

According to informants consulted at Walwal and Qolan in the Worder and Gelaldin study districts respectively, the practice of trucking small ruminants to pasture fields has also helped pastoralists and traders to reduce the risk of trade animals being confiscated by the Ethiopian army. As trucking small ruminants to better pasture located on both sides of the border including for fattening purpose is now a common practice, traders and pastoralists secured the right to argue against the real destination of their trade animals loaded on Lorries. From PPR transmission perspective, this practice of trucking small ruminants to distant located potential pasture fields both from within the region and ports means that the clinically sick animals as well as those at their incubation phase of the disease can easily spread the disease far beyond their normal territory.

4.3 Estimating the Effect of Drought and Livestock Market to Spread Disease

The between-district/region transmission modeling approaches are classified into two categories: models that attempt to explicitly model different between-district/region transmission routes or mechanisms and more economical models that describe the combined effect of all possible routes and develop them together into one model. The first type of models is denoted as 'drought-factored' and the second as 'market' (see Figures 5 and 6).

When using the drought-factored models to make extrapolations to scenarios that differed according to the susceptibility of the host and influx populations, all model parameters are estimated from the observational data of the last two outbreaks. Between-district transmission in areas where there was no vaccination in both infected and susceptible populations prior to onset of outbreak affected disease-free population migrated in search of pasture at infected foci was also hypothesized to see the effects of vaccination on further transmission. Example, emergency vaccination of influx susceptible population at outbreak site and herds remained behind at home, and even large scale preventive vaccination, and explored the use of risk maps to define high-risk areas for PPR spread and evaluate the effects of local livestock markets in such areas.

Figure 5: A schematic representation of drought-factored models of PPR transmission

Figure 6: A schematic representation of trade animals-based models of PPR transmission

4.4 Predicting the Course of Drought-factored PPR Outbreak

Table 9 presents the epizootic course of PPR outbreak that may be factored by drought. The most probable period of exposure and peaks of outbreaks in the different susceptible populations presented in the table are based on the normal timing of gu and deyr rains: April to June and October to December respectively. Normal practice amongst the pastoralists in drought situations is to start moving herds to distant located pasture and water in the second month of the failed rain season and return them home toward the beginning of the subsequent rainy season assuming that it will be time to then move to different direction if it delays.

As a consequence, the peaks of primary, secondary and tertiary generations of cases spaced by incubation period are expected during the first month of the influx population's stay period. As such, vaccination of susceptible population that is going to mix with infected population at departure or arrival may help preventing the secondary and tertiary generations of cases at least. Technically, it is essential that emergency vaccination during drought-factored outbreak targets the susceptible population both at settlement sites and

¹ Animals exposed to infected ones at local market that may be returned home and/or production animals purchased from market by farmers can be possible source of infection.

destination of flocks migrated to infected area in search of pasture and water. In reality, it may not be possible to reach the susceptible populations likely migrating to known endemic areas such as Somalia and Kenya in search of pasture and water during critical drought situation. Where timely vaccination of an outbreak-affected susceptible population migrated to endemic area located within or outside the region in search of pasture and water appears possible, the veterinary unit of host district needs to prioritize the influx population with emergency vaccination to reduce the number of generations of cases.

As can be seen in Figure 1, when an infected influx population imports the disease to provisionally disease-free area, the risk of drought-factored outbreak further spreading through market route is also a case for concern. For instance, external traders may take the advantage of massive market supply and low price of drought-affected animals in transporting infected animals to highland areas for fattening purpose. Technically, it is essential that the strategy for the progressive control of PPR in Ethiopia adopts a national approach to model construction and parameter quantification of PPR transmission between different regions, zones and districts as well as the way in which vaccination affects the market route of transmission.

One emerging issue is the effect that the new practice of pastoralists trucking animals from kebele/district to kebele/district can have on the disease transmission. This may lead to changes in the transmission risks between unvaccinated populations, in comparison to risks estimated from the most recent outbreaks in this modeling. For these reasons, the drought-factored outbreak transmission model described in this report needs to be redefined with herders in each area.

In general, the author strongly believes that national strategy needs to experiment an emergency early warning and response system that treats boarder areas of Somali and Oromia regions such as lowland districts of the east Hararge, west Harargie, Bale, Borena and Guji zones as a single entity in coordinating emergency vaccination in the event of PPR outbreak. The best example of the current practice is the emergency vaccinations intervened in Babile area in response to drought-factored outbreak affected flocks migrated from Somali region specifically Dhereto to Midhega district of Oromia region in 2011/12. Typically, those emergency vaccinations triggered by a drought-factored outbreak started following susceptible flocks owned by Somali herder to Medhega district of Oromia were based on regional administrative divisions, with the emergency vaccination implemented first by Oromia region.

For most of the outbreak events in the last three years (2012 to 2014), the pastoralists did not mention external source of infection and, as a result, the data do not allow useful estimations of the parameters for specific routes. Therefore, models consider different scenarios and routes, such as drought-induced migration and trade animal movements. Infect, the models aim to guide the programming of control measures such as vaccine interventions and implementers when trying to evaluate vaccination strategies that have different impacts on different routes.

Table 9: Epizootic course of PPR outbreak that can be factored by drought

Event	Most probable period of event
Migration of drought-affected susceptible population to infected areas with better pasture and water resources	Early May and November when the gu and deyr season rains perform poor respectively
Onset of outbreak following arrival	2 nd half of May and November depending on the month of arrival, i.e. around ten days after exposure to infection
Peaks of primary, secondary and tertiary generations of cases spaced by incubation period outbreak	End of May to mid June, and end of November to mid December depending on the month of exposure, i.e. first 30 days after arrival
End of outbreak	Early July and December, i.e. around one month period from onset
Drought-affected population moves back to own territory or far to comparatively better pasture and water resources	End of March to early April and end of August to early October, i.e. normal start time of the post- drought gu and deyr season rains s
Onset of outbreak at home place or new destination of the infected population evacuated	Mid April and October, i.e. around two-week period following the arrival herds migrated to infected area
Peaks of primary, secondary and tertiary generations of cases spaced by incubation period outbreak	End of May and November, i.e. first 30 days after arrival of migrated herds
Outbreak ceases	End of June and December

4.5 Estimating the Impact of Emergency Vaccination on Outbreak Course

Vaccination against PPR is a well-established prophylactic tool, and is currently used in many regions involved in the strategy for progressive control of PPR in Ethiopia. Large-scale vaccination strategies have been successful in realizing the eradication of a closely related disease 'RP' from the world. In PPR endemic pastoral areas of Ethiopia, vaccination on a large scale will start soon and the incidence of outbreaks is expected to decline to zero in about 2 years.

One particularly difficult issue in the strategy for progressive control of PPR is the absence of other control measures like movement restriction replaced with emergency vaccination while trade animals are moving between zones and regions. This may lead to changes in the transmission risks between endemic and disease-free areas, as trade animals can easily disseminate the disease over wider areas. Clearly, the model for the effect of vaccination on between-region transmission cannot be informed by the data on outbreaks occurred in the Somali Region during the last three years alone. Further confidence in the current vaccination program is generally low both in terms of timing and coverage though differs between highland and pastoral areas. In the study region, on average, the time interval between onset of the outbreaks and vaccination conducted in years 2014, 2013 and 2012 was around 1.57, 2.5 and 3.3 months respectively (Table 12).

On average, the percentage of kebeles covered by vaccination programs conducted in 2012, 2013 and 2014 was around 63.4% (736/1,160) of the total number of kebeles under the

targeted districts for which vaccination data was obtained from district veterinary service data (Table 11). As pastoralist informants were unaware of vaccinations conducted elsewhere in their district, some of the information on vaccination events were purely based on interviews carried out with government animal health professionals.

The duration of outbreaks triggered the emergency vaccinations assessed was around 4 months on average (Table 12). Although the virus can establish infection in relatively small populations of susceptible animals, large populations are necessary for the infection to sustain. The 4-month long average outbreak period suggest that cases to have occurred over more than a single incubation periods, and effective vaccine interventions may have resulted in shorter duration of those outbreaks.

The around four-month outbreak lifespan also implies that emergency vaccination is an appropriate intervention at all stages of the PPR outbreak, and it looks like there were about eight generations of cases spaced by an average incubation period of around 5 days. As such, timely and effective vaccination might have helped decreasing the outbreak period to less than two months. If possible, the better option is to conduct vaccination in all endemic districts of the region at once in the absence of outbreak.

Table 10: Timelines- major PPR outbreak and vaccination events in the study areas

Location	Location and Year of PPR outbreak and vaccination events					
	2014		2013		2012	
	Outbreak	Vaccination	Outbreak	Vaccination	Outbreak	Vaccination
Babile (Dhereto)	Jun	Aug		Apr		Jun
Kebribeyah (Dible)	Jun	Aug		Mar		Sep
Harshin (Belasie)	Jul	Aug		Apr		Jul
Gashamo (Lansol)		Feb	Dec			
Shinele (Dhegahjebis)	Jun	Aug		Mar		Mar
Erer (Melkashekh)	Apr	Jul		Jul		Jul
Warder (Walwal)	Jun	Jun		Feb		Jan
Galadin (Qolan)	Feb	Mar		Nov		
Hargelle (Drinder)		Jan	Dec			Feb
Hargelle (Dualle)		Jan	Oct			Feb
Hargelle (Idher)		Jan		Jan		Feb
Cherati (Hayir)		Mar		May		
Cherati (Gerar)		Mar	Nov			
Cherati (Dereto)		Mar	Mar			
Dollo bay (Helquran)			Mar	May		Jun
Dollo baay (Mader)				Nov	May	Jun
Mustahil						
Adadle					Mar	Aug
Kelafo						Nov
Dollo Ado	Feb	Apr				
Filtu	Jun	Nov				
Dhekasuftu		May	Nov			

Source: Interviews with government experts and CAHW

Table 11: PPR outbreak and vaccination data

Event	Event repetitions		
	2014	2013	2012
Year			
Total number of sites investigated for outbreak	28	28	28
Total number of outbreaks reported from study districts	13	12	8
Total number of vaccinations conducted in study districts	22	23	15
Number of vaccination conducted following outbreaks	11	13	8
Interval between onset of outbreak and vaccination , month	1.57	2.5	3.3
Vaccines deployed per district in dose, average	938,000	1,045,000	525,000
Total kebeles of vaccine intervention study districts	301	217	147
kebeles covered in the vaccine intervention districts	181	153	11
Small ruminants vaccinated per kebele, average	5,182	6,830	4,730

Table 12: Interval between onset of outbreak and vaccination events

Location	Outbreak period in month		Interval between onset of outbreak and vaccination			Minimum interval between last two outbreaks in month
	Last outbreak	Previous outbreak	2013/14(month)	2013/12 (month)	2012/11 (month)	
Dhereto	4	6	2			25
Dible	4	4	2			3
Belasie	3	4	1			12
Lansol	4			2		120
Dhegahjebis	4	4	2			14
Melkashekh	5	4	3			20
Walwal	4	5	0			55
Qolan	6	9	1			3
Drinder	3	3		1		25
Dualle	3	3		3		52
Idher	4					120
Hayir	3					120
Gerar	4			4		120
Dereto	3					120
Helaquran	3	5			2	26
Mader	3	3			2	28
Mustahil	4					120
Adadle	4				6	120
Kelaf	There was not outbreak during the last 10 years					
Average	3.78	4.54	1.57	2.5	3.33	61.28

Source: Focus group discussions

4.6 Understanding PPR Outbreak Occurrence Patterns in Somali Region

Figure 7 illustrates the number of PPR outbreaks reported by pastoralists and local animal health professionals to have occurred during the study period, 2008 to 2014. The number of new outbreaks witnessed in different parts of the region in 2014 until September was the highest in 7 years time. In this regard, it is unlikely that the community and government animal health experts under failed to recall PPR outbreaks occurred earlier at least between 2008 and 2011. Further majority of the PPR vaccinations conducted in the study areas were supported by FAO, as well as NGOs operating in the vaccine intervention areas that makes the probability of outbreak not being reported nearly nil.

In Moyale area, the community had to blame drought-affected population migrated to the area from the Kenyan side of the boarder in search of pasture and water for PPR outbreak started in September 2014. Although some of the outbreaks occurred due to either susceptible population migrated to endemic area such as from Babile to Medhega or infected population hosted in the case Moyale, there was no direct correlation noted between specific outbreak and drought events in majority of the cases. Further majority of the outbreaks were said to have started at the beginning and end of the rainy seasons, indicating that drought-induced migration might not be the key factor led-to those outbreaks. For example, 18 out of 33 outbreaks occurred between year 2012 and 2014 were said to have started during the two rainy seasons, gu (April to June) and deyr (September and November). On average, the interval between consecutive outbreaks was around 5 years (Table 12). Therefore, the susceptible population increased over time could be a more important factor for outbreak patterns illustrated in Figure 3 than drought.

The 5-year interval between two consecutive outbreaks and the number of outbreaks increased in 2014 may suggest an alternative hypothesis that '*PPR outbreak can occur anywhere in pastoral areas anytime*'. The point is that the strategy for progressive control of PPR should consider all zones and districts as endemic area, as it seems the proportion of susceptible population has been on increasing, probably because either the proportion of adult animals developed immunity from natural infection decreased below some critical level, or the small-scale vaccinations conducted to control the disease during the recent years.

In general, the highest number of outbreaks occurred in year 2014 appears an issue of critical concern. A further concern is that some of the PPR outbreak rumors especially the ones occurred between July and September 2014 such as in Moyale and Hudet areas have not been investigated by national and regional laboratories as of end of September 2014, perhaps even not reported to the concerned body by district veterinary service.

Figure 7: PPR outbreaks occurred in Somali region since 2008

4.7 Estimating Changes in Susceptible Population due to Vaccination

Table 13 provides population sex composition data from proportional pilings conducted by focus group discussion participants, and reproductively performance data obtained from women key informants during this study. A formula applied to estimate proportion eligible for vaccination of the total goat and sheep populations at the beginning and end of the two-year vaccination intended under the strategy for progressive control of PPR in Ethiopia calculates 80.3% and 5%, and 76.8% and 5.87% ≥ 6 month old goat and sheep population respectively.

The assumptions in the calculations were the proportion of susceptible goats and sheep eligible populations could be derived from data on flock age and sex composition, birthing interval and births surviving to weaning age from FGDs and key informant interviews, see Table 4. Another important assumption in the projection of population that can possibly value vaccination each round during the two-year vaccine intervention period was that vaccination would be conducted twice per year at 6 month intervals and during the rainy seasons, gu (April to June) and deyr (October to November). As these are the main birthing seasons, animals born during a given rainy season will then be vaccinated at the age of six month during the subsequent rainy season.

Table 13: Estimate susceptible goat and sheep populations by vaccination round

Goat	Susceptible population	<6month	Eligible for vaccination	80%	Balance
Round 1	100	19.7	80.3	64.24	16.06
Round 2	35.76	19.7	35.76	28.61	7.15
Round 3	26.85	19.7	26.85	21.48	5.37
Round 4	25.07	19.7	25.07	20.06	5.01
Sheep	Susceptible population	<6month	Eligible for vaccination	80%	Balance
Round 1	100	23.2	76.8	61.44	15.36
Round 2	38.56	23.2	38.56	30.848	7.71
Round 3	30.91	23.2	30.91	24.73	6.18
Round 4	29.38	23.2	29.38	23.50	5.87

5. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESSTIONS

While the majority of PPR outbreaks in the past have been diagnosed based on clinical signs, there was 26 outbreaks occurred between 2012 and 2014 in the 20 districts covered by this outbreak investigation work. On average, one out of every two districts included in the outbreak investigation has been affected by PPR outbreak during the study period, 2012 to 2014 until September. Several PPR outbreaks may go unrecorded in remote parts of the region due to inadequate animal disease reporting and surveillance systems.

Routine epidemiological survey of PPR outbreak has not been possible so far due to resource constraint, and partly because the PPR is treated like any other endemic diseases. This is now changing in Somali region as the Federal veterinary service, VSF Suisse and other key stakeholders like FAO in the strategy for progressive control of PPR in Ethiopia are adopting a more coordinated approach to investigation and control of the disease, and this study will aid in tracking future outbreaks while also informing is expected to inform more about the limitations of the current practices including vaccination.

The author understands that tracking PPR outbreaks in some geographical locations such as Nogob zone is not possible due to security reason, however, measuring economic losses resulting from PPR outbreak, and studying the epidemiology of the disease in all accessible parts of the region is essential as it helps to influence policy makers both at region and federal levels for them to direct more attention to the strategy for progressive control of PPR in Ethiopia. As access to insecure areas like Nogob zone is critical determinant of success in the strategy for progressive control of PPR in Ethiopia that work toward eradication of the disease from the country, taking the issue to higher officials may be helpful in identifying alternative outbreak investigation and vaccination option such as the use of army and CAHWs.

While the outbreak-affected districts subsequently become endemic to the disease, the recovered animals are protected from re-infection for the remainder of their lives. In this study, recovery rates from PPRV infection in previously affected population is around 52.3 per cent on average. Considerably lower proportion of the population has also been immunized through vaccination.

If the findings from this rapid field observation are substantiated by more comprehensive serological surveillance, they may have far reaching implications for PPR control strategies in the country. Though the sample size in this study was limited and may not be a true representation of the target population, the present investigation provided preliminary information on PPR outbreak patterns in the small ruminant population of Somali Region.

More intensive investigations of a similar nature, taking into account disparities in sheep and goat production systems and the market routes affecting the pattern of the outbreak transmission, are required. These factors are indirectly influenced by socio-economic factors, the migration patterns of small ruminants in relation to season, flock size and the

population intensity of the animals. Such studies are only possible in collaboration with the Federal veterinary service, the National Animal Health, Diagnostic and Investigation Center (NAHDIC) and Regional Veterinary Diagnostic and Research Laboratory (RVDRL).

Concerning the economic importance of small ruminant production and diseases to the Somali pastoralists, while goat and sheep account for around 55 per cent of the total livestock population of the area, around 50 per cent of loss resulting due to all reasons including drought is caused by disease of which contagious diseases specifically CCPP, PPR and pox that can be prevented with vaccine contributed 70 per cent of the total loss attributed to disease problems. With respect to PPR, the proportion infected during the last outbreak occurred in each study area was estimated to around 51 per cent of the total population of the area, with around 29 per cent of the cases ended fatal on average.

Drought-induced animal movement appeared to be the most important between district, region and country PPR transmission route in the case of Somali region. Typically outbreak transmitted between Shinille and Erer districts in 2008/9, Oromia and Somali region in Babile area in 2012 as well as unverified outbreak reported from Moyale area in September 2014 following influx of herds from Kenyan side are attributed to livestock movements made in search of pasture and water.

Further the between-district/region transmission modeling approaches followed in this study report that describe the combined effect of all possible routes of transmission suggest that role of the market route increases with drought particularly when an infected population migrates to disease free area. For example, once infected herds from Kenya imported the disease to Ethiopia in Moyale areas, the risk of infected animals marketed from among influx and host populations at their incubation stage to the local being trucked over longer distance to highland markets is expected to increase proportional to proximity and probability of animals to be sold to local markets both.

Due to an ongoing increase in drought frequency as well as trade animal movements, the market transmission route will have a more multiplier impact in the future. The practice of Somali pastoralists in Worder area trucking small ruminants across boarder to ports and from ports to potential grazing area with water like that of Qolan in Galadin district being used as holding grounds by small ruminant export companies based in Somaliland is another critical concern.

Therefore, when using the market and drought-factored models described in this report to make extrapolations to scenarios that differ according to the geographic location of concern, it is essential that all model parameters are treated together. The direct correlation between market and drought-factored PPR transmission models displayed in this report is a particularly difficult challenge in the strategy for progressive control of PPR. This may lead to changes in the transmission risks between endemic and disease-free areas, as trade animals can easily disseminate the disease over wider areas.

Clearly, the model for the drought-factored transmission indicates the effect of emergency vaccination on between-region transmission to be minimal unless coordinated between the

regions affected by that particular outbreak. Further role of the current inter-region coordination or information exchange system is generally low both in terms of timeliness and effectiveness of the response to outbreaks. Therefore, the establishment of functional inter-region coordination system is one of the decisions that must involve presidents of regional governments.

A minimal number of small ruminants in Somali region have been vaccinated during the last 3 years or so. Current plans for the implementation of strategy for progressive control of PPR in Ethiopia will probably change the coverage of vaccinations and subsequently the epidemiology of PPRV virus in the region. However, the vaccination plan needs to account for the population dynamics of the goat and sheep flocks. The sales off-take of male goats at an early age combined with the high fecundity of these species results in around 38 per cent of the goat population being replaced each year.

Initially, in order to reduce economic losses due to PPRV, intensive vaccination of the entire population within a specified area would need to be undertaken. Subsequent vaccinations would then be performed on six monthly bases to vaccinate younger animals at approximately 6 months of age.